

Differential effects of employment status on work-related outcomes: A pilot study of permanent and casual workers in Sri Lanka

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Purpose- To investigate whether permanent workers with standard employment that is protected and casual workers with long-term employment that is not protected but performing the same core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting exhibit different work-related outcomes.

Design/methodology/approach- Permanent workers and casual workers holding core jobs with long-term employment responded to the survey questionnaire. Logistic regression was used for the data analysis.

Findings- Job satisfaction, procedural justice and work performance were found as important work-related outcomes that discriminate between permanent and casual workers.

Originality/value- Although consequences of different employment arrangements would be of interest to many organisations world wide, on the one hand, little empirical research has compared work-related outcomes of permanent workers with casuals (holding same core functions with long-term employment) or permanent workers with workers in any form of nonstandard employment arrangement. On the other hand, the literature on the use of labour flexibility strategies are mainly concentrated to developed market economies. If organisations use casual workers alongside permanent workers in core jobs, there is a need of examining implications of such practices. The findings of this study establish baseline data that would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Keywords: Casual employment, nonstandard employment, permanent employment, Sri Lanka.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

The changing pattern of work arrangement is a salient feature of the contemporary employment environment and one that has received considerable attention in the literature (e.g. Chattopadhyay and George, 2001; Connell and Burgess, 2002; Lansbury, 2009; Standing, 2008; Zeytinoglu et al., 2004). Organisations find themselves in the need of increased flexibility within their workforce to promote efficiency and competitiveness that deemed necessary in the global marketplace (Ilcan et al., 2003; Jung and Tak, 2008). One way to respond to the

demand of flexibility is to rely on nonstandard employment arrangements (Ilcan et al., 2003; Nollen and Axel, 1996). The term “nonstandard” is used to distinguish a variety of employment arrangements, such as casual, from the “standard” model of full-time, year-round, permanent employment with statutory benefits and job security (Leighton and Painter, 2001; Louie et al., 2006). Evidence suggests that there is a growing move towards a variety of nonstandard employment arrangements (Burgess et al., 2008; Standing, 2008).

The use of nonstandard employment arrangements cannot be seen as a strategy on its own, but must be considered as a part of the total approach of an organisation towards its people management (Burgess et al., 2008; Standing, 2008). The use of non-standard employment arrangements reflects a desire on behalf of management to increase the alignment of labour resources to the needs of the organization (Buultjens, 2001; Lowry et al, 2002) rather than commitments to meet equal or fair opportunity motivations to assist employees (Twinaime et al, 2006). The focus of this research, however, is different from the flexible firm model (Atkinson, 1984; Hanratty, 2000) because in the flexible firm model the core employees and the peripheral employees undertake different job tasks. The focus of this study is on employees in the permanent employment arrangement and non-standard employment arrangement, casual in particular, who perform same core job tasks side-by-side in the same work setting. Hence, for many people, standard full-time permanent employment along with its associated benefits has been replaced with casual employment arrangement. Therefore, some of the consequences of using nonstandard employment arrangements are changes in the internal labour market structure (Saloniemi and Zeytinoglu, 2007) and proliferation of inferior jobs in the labour market (Burgess and Campbell 1998; Campbell 2001; Watson, 2005). Hence, such a use of casual employment arrangement suggests declining stability and security in the employment and a growing irregular labour force. Scholars, therefore, suggest this move as an indicative of a qualitative shift in the regulation of employment relations (Ilcan et al., 2003).

Therefore, the literature identifies work status (i.e., whether permanent or casual) as a major determinant of the exchange relationship between individuals and the employing

organization (Ang and Slaughter, 2001; Storey et al., 2002). The work status could have a significant effect when both permanent and casual workers perform same job tasks side-by-side in the same work setting. Specifically, work status influences employer obligations such as pay, benefits, access to job related training, opportunities for advancement, and job security (Ang and Slaughter, 2001; Campbell, 1996; Lowry et al, 2002). For instance, past studies identified casual employment as an unprotected form of employment with the absence of many standard benefits, rights and forms of protection such as less income security, job security, and access to job-related training compared to permanent employment (e.g. Campbell, 1996; Campbell and Burgess, 2001; Layte et al., 2008; Lowry et al, 2002; MacPhail and Bowles, 2008; Standing, 2008). Hence, some researchers argue that being employed as a casual worker would suggest being treated as a second-class citizen by both employer and fellow permanent workers (e.g., Campbell and Burgess, 2001). In this context, the literature provides rationale for proposing that permanent and casual workers holding core jobs with long-term employment working side-by-side within the same organisation could have different work-related attitudes based on the specifics of their exchange relationship because of their work status (Ang and Slaughter, 2001; Buultjens, 2001; Watson, 2005). Attitudes and behaviours of these two categories of workers are, therefore, important as those are related to important work outcomes, such as performance (Ang and Slaughter, 2001; Buultjens, 2001).

Although links between labour flexibility strategies and employee attitudes have been established in the Western research (e.g. Becker and Huselid 1999; Brewster et al., 1997; Mayne et al., 1996), to date, there has been a paucity of research conducted on permanent and casual operator level workers who perform same job tasks side-by-side in the same manufacturing floor. On the one hand, there has been little empirical research that compared work-related outcomes of permanent workers with casuals (holding core functions with long-term employment) or permanent workers with workers in any form of nonstandard employment arrangement (e.g. Ang and Slaughter, 2001; Gramm and Schnell, 2001; Kunda et al., 2002; Olsen, 2006). Therefore, little is known about casual workers' attitudes towards their work environment and whether their attitudes differ from their fellow permanent counterparts

(Kessler et al., 1999). On the other hand, the literature on different employment arrangements and their consequences are mainly concentrated to developed market economies in the North America, Europe, Australia and New Zealand (see Houseman and Osawa, 2003; Louie et al., 2006). Our review of literature failed to find empirical studies conducted on this area in less industrialised economies, where firms are continually in search for increased labour flexibility to maintain their competitiveness in the global marketplace. If organisations use casual workers alongside permanent workers in core jobs, there is a need of examining work-related outcomes of permanent and casual workers and implications of such practices.

In the above context, the specific objective of the study is to investigate whether permanent workers with standard employment that is protected and casuals with long-term employment that is not protected but performing the same core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting exhibit different work-related outcomes, namely, job satisfaction, organisational justice, and work performance. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide useful information to better understand work-related attitudes of permanent and casual workers. By doing so, this study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Consistent with the objective, the rest of the paper briefly describes the Sri Lankan context related to the study and reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Sri Lankan context - permanent and casual employment arrangements

The employer-employee relationship in Sri Lanka is based on the Common Law concept of Master and Servant under the Roman Dutch Law (Chandra, n.d.). The relationship between employer and employee may be characterised as a voluntary relationship into which the parties may enter on terms laid down by themselves, within limitations imposed only by the general law of contract (Chandra, n.d.). The definitions of the terms "employee" and "employer" in the

statutes regarding labour legislation are the best sources available in determining the nature of the relationship between the two parties. In addition, case law has assisted in establishing this relationship (Chandra, n.d.).

The employment arrangements in Sri Lanka are of different types. The permanent employment arrangement, which can be best understood as a contract for an indefinite term, is the central form. The permanent employment has been installed in Sri Lanka as both dominant form of employment and as the standard entry-point for access to a comprehensive set of industrial rights and benefits (Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, 1997). Outside this framework lays nonstandard employment arrangements, such as, casual, probationary, seasonal, fixed-term and that of an apprentice. Casual employment arrangement is widely recognised in Sri Lanka as one of the main forms of nonstandard waged work.

A casual worker is one employed by chance and they will be offered work as and when work is available. An employer cannot expect a casual worker to arrive work continuously: casual worker can report for work as and when he/she desires. Further, casual workers cannot as of a right expect work from the employer. They are seen as workers who are used “as and when required”, with each engagement being seen as a separate engagement. Furthermore, although permanent workers have a period of notice in the termination of employment, casual workers can be terminated or fail to be re-engaged at any time. By its very nature casual employment cannot confer upon a workman a right to reinstatement as there is no former position in which he/she can be restored as in the case of a permanent worker (Chandra, n.d.).

There are attempts by many employers to resort to the concept of "casual employment" in order to avoid permanent employment (Chandra, n.d.). Hence, in Sri Lanka, the category of casual employment includes at its core the type of occasional and irregular work, but it may also include a broad penumbra of work that may be long-term and regular but that is deprived of standard employment benefits. In other words, in addition to the group of “true casuals”, there may be a group of “long-term casuals”, whose participation in casual employment is characterised by lengthy tenure and substantial regularity in daily and weekly hours of employment (Chandra, n.d.). However, such employment arrangements have been proved to

be unsuccessful when challenged in Courts in Sri Lanka. Apart from Shop and Office Employee's Act of 1954, there is no other statute in Sri Lanka, which imposes an obligation on the employer to issue a letter of employment to employees. So, in the absence of a letter of appointment and sometimes in the absence of documentation to establish such a relationship, the distinction of the actual relationship becomes important (Chandra, n.d.). Therefore, a description or designation on a document where the workman may have agreed to be designated as a casual worker is not conclusive in Sri Lanka. The actual relationship between the parties will be examined in Courts to bring about a satisfactory solution. If it is revealed that the employer had treated the worker as a person with a permanent character, then he/she will not be treated as a casual worker in Courts in Sri Lanka (Chandra, n.d.).

Theoretical background and hypothesis

Employment status is a major determinant of the exchange relationship between individuals and the employing organisation (Storey et al., 2002; Wilson et al., 2008). The literature suggests that casual employment does not measure up well on many dimensions of security that constitute permanent employment (Paramio and Zofio, 2008; Standing, 2008). For instance, evidence suggests that casual workers have less opportunities for training, apprenticeship and education to acquire and refine capabilities and to make use of capabilities compared to permanent workers (e.g. Layte et al., 2008; MacPhail and Bowles, 2008; Paramio and Zofio, 2008; Standing, 2008; Wilson et al., 2008).

Further, casual workers experience poor working conditions contributing to work insecurity (e.g. MacPhail and Bowles, 2008). They are provided with little access to workplace time flexibility strategies, where casual workers feel unable to turn down inconvenient hours (e.g. MacPhail and Bowles, 2008). MacPhail and Bowles (2008) suggest that “permanent workers, especially shift workers, may experience family stress but the uncertainty of hours for casual workers adds an extra layer and can be captured by the concept of time insecurity” (MacPhail and Bowles, 2008, p. 109).

Furthermore, casual workers experience low job autonomy (e.g. Layte et al., 2008) and perceive low skill variety (e.g. Wilson et al., 2008) than permanent workers. Overall, casual employment can be identified as an unprotected form of employment with the absence of many standard benefits, rights and forms of protection such as income security, job security, and access to job-related training compared to permanent employment (e.g. Campbell, 1996; Campbell and Burgess, 2001; Houseman and Osawa, 2003; Layte et al., 2008; MacPhail and Bowles, 2008; Paramio and Zofío, 2008; Standing, 2008). Therefore, scholars suggest that upsides in employment conditions of casual status are harder to identify (e.g. Burgess et al., 2008; Standing, 2008) and casual workers do not enjoy full workplace citizenship (see Watson, 2005).

The literature also suggests that given the differential treatment to casual workers relative to permanent workers, they are likely to have poorer perceptions of the organisation and are likely to exhibit poorer work-related outcomes (e.g. MacPhail and Bowles, 2008; Paramio and Zofío, 2008; Standing, 2008). For instance, firms could gain competitive advantage over their competitors through employee commitment rather than compliance with rules (Connell and Burgess, 2002). However, commitment is a part of the relational contract that excludes workers in nonstandard arrangements (Connell and Burgess, 2002). Hence, evidence suggests that casual workers lack commitment (e.g. Standing, 2008) and may experience a low degree of job satisfaction (e.g. Paramio and Zofío, 2008). Further, casuals lack the sense of attachment to a particular job (MacPhail and Bowles, 2008), and they do not become embroiled in the organisation's culture (see Connell and Burgess, 2002). Furthermore, casualization tends to depress workplace innovations and makes workers not care for equipment or raw materials, resulting in high non-labour costs. Evidence also suggests that casualization induces workers to lower productivity (Standing, 2008, p. 26). In addition, it is suggested that workers in standard arrangement (unlike casuals) are more likely to put pressure on management to improve working conditions and efficiency in order to obtain decent profits (e.g. Standing, 2008).

The literature on nonstandard employment identifies two recent moves in employment relations. First, nonstandard workers, casuals in particular, are identified to form a permanent minority share in the labour force, where they are found to be employed at the same workplace for lengthy periods of tenure (e.g. Louie et al., 2006; Pocock et al., 2004; Zeytinoglu et al., 2004). For instance, Pocock et al. (2004) and Louie et al. (2006) identify a situation of “permanent casuals” where casual workers often hold long-term and regular jobs having lengthy periods of tenure.

Second, the literature describes a division between core and peripheral functions based on the assumption that certain jobs in an organisation are more vital than that of others (Gramm and Schnell, 2001; Magnum et al., 1985; Matusik and Hill, 1998). Core functions are assumed to be performed by regular workers who enjoy continuous employment while peripheral functions are assumed to be performed by workers who are loosely connected to the organisation, such as casuals (Olsen, 2006). However, the literature suggests a recent move towards using nonstandard workers in core activities and integrate them with regular workers (e.g. Gramm and Schnell, 2001; Lautsch, 2002; Olsen, 2006). When casual workers are found to often work side-by-side with the regular workers, the picture of these workers as inferior to regular workers is challenged (e.g. Matusik and Hill, 1998). In this regard, a blended workforce of standard and nonstandard workers is found to have consequences for behavioural outcomes in organisations (e.g. Chattopadhyay and George, 2001; Davis-Blake et al., 2003; Geary, 1992). For instance, Geary (1992) reports incidences of regular workers giving orders to nonstandard workers around. Further, Davis-Blake et al. (2003) found that a blended workforce of standard and nonstandard workers negatively influence the relationship between managers and workers.

Overall, the recent developments discussed above suggests that nonstandard workers, whose duration of employment clearly indicates that they are long-term casuals (and not on a short term, needs basis) but who do not receive in principle the same benefits as regular workers, perform job tasks that are not necessarily peripheral. These recent moves in employment relations have implications for the concept of nonstandard work. Therefore,

scholars such as Connelly and Gallagher (2004) and Olsen (2006) highlight the importance of increased research on the consequences of such nonstandard work practices for organisations. Further, scholars suggest the need of research in this area in different country contexts to better understand the phenomenon (e.g. Olsen, 2006). Therefore, the focus of this paper is on permanent workers in standard employment and casual workers, whose duration of employment clearly indicates that they are long-term casuals, performing the same core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting in Sri Lanka. Based on the above reviewed literature, on the one hand, the presence of long-term casuals performing the same core jobs along with permanent workers signals an important element of dualism within the employment structure, where casuals are targets of differential treatment compared to permanent workers. On the other hand, the literature reviewed above on standard and nonstandard employment (e.g. Connell and Burgess, 2002; Jung and Tak, 2008; MacPhail and Bowles, 2008; Paramio and Zofio, 2008) and the specific literature on standard and nonstandard workers with long-term employment holding core jobs (e.g. Chattopadhyay and George, 2001; Davis-Blake et al., 2003; Geary, 1992; Olsen, 2006), suggest that employment status might have an effect on work-related outcomes of workers. Therefore, for this study it is proposed that relative to permanent workers, casual workers with long-term employment that is not protected but holding the same core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting are likely to exhibit poorer work-related outcomes. On the basis of our reading of the literature reviewed above and preliminary investigations made by us about work outcomes that are important when employing casual and permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting in Sri Lanka, this paper investigates differences between permanent and casual workers in work-related outcomes of job satisfaction, organisational justice, and work performance.

As a result of many decades of efforts by researchers, there appears to be a high level of agreement among scholars on the meaning of constructs of job satisfaction (see Price 1997), organisational justice (e.g. Cheung and Law, 2008; Colquitt et al., 2001), and work performance (e.g. Rodwell et al., 1998). In brief, job satisfaction is defined as “the degree to

which employees have a positive affective orientation towards employment by the organization” (Vroom, 1964, pp. 99-105). Job satisfaction is seen as a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job experiences (Locke, 1976). Therefore, job satisfaction is a fairly complex job-related attitudinal variable. It reveals an affective reaction to a job that results from a person’s comparison of actual outcomes with those that are desired, anticipated or deserved. Based on the literature reviewed above on permanent and casual workers, it is expected that the level of job satisfaction between permanent and casual workers will be different. Therefore, it is hypothesized for the study:

Hypothesis 1: Perceptions towards job satisfaction of permanent workers and casual workers (with long-term employment holding core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting) will be significantly different. It is expected that casuals will demonstrate poorer perceptions in job satisfaction compared to permanent workers.

Organizational justice refers to employees' perception of fairness caused by organizational practices (Greenberg 1987). In this study, we distinguish between distributive and procedural justice (see Folger and Konovsky, 1989; McFarlin and Sweeney, 1992). Distributive justice refers to the perceived fairness of various job outcomes employees receive such as job assignments. Procedural justice relates to the perceived fairness of the means, rules and/or procedures used to determine those outcomes, for example to assign jobs (Ang and Slaughter, 2001; Roch and Shanock, 2006). Previous research found that these two dimensions of organizational justice to be related, albeit differentially, to employee work-related attitudes and behaviours (Colquitt et al., 2001). Based on the literature reviewed above on permanent and casual workers, it is expected that the perceptions towards organizational justice between permanent and casual workers will be different. Therefore, it is hypothesized for the study:

Hypothesis 2: Perceptions towards distributive justice of permanent workers and casual workers (with long-term employment holding core jobs along with permanent

workers side-by-side in the same work setting) will be significantly different. It is expected that casuals will demonstrate poorer perceptions in organizational justice compared to permanent workers.

Hypothesis 3: Perceptions towards procedural justice of permanent workers and casual workers (with long-term employment holding core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting) will be significantly different. It is expected that casuals will demonstrate poorer perceptions in organizational justice compared to permanent workers.

With regard to work performance, the aim of many management practices is to enhance worker and ultimately organizational performance (Rodwell et al., 1998). Performance implicitly means doing better or worse than comparable other (Price, 1997). Generally, self-report measures of individual performance were considered more appropriate because the individual is uniquely aware of the elements of high performance, and when the focus is on the perspective of the individual employee (Bommer et al., 1995). Based on the literature reviewed above on permanent and casual workers, it is expected that the perceptions towards work performance between permanent and casual workers will be different. Therefore, it is hypothesized for the study:

Hypothesis 4: Perceptions towards work performance of permanent workers and casual workers (with long-term employment holding core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting) will be significantly different. It is expected that casuals will demonstrate poorer perceptions in work performance compared to permanent workers.

It should be noted that the findings of the previous research studies have suggested several interrelationships between work-related variables. For instance, Dailey and Kirk (1992) suggested a possibility that distributive and procedural justice may lead to job satisfaction.

However, as an initial attempt, interrelationships between work outcomes are beyond the focus of this study and have not been investigated as a result.

Methodology

Empirical research context and sample

The current study was focused on one organization. The reasons for confining the study to a single organization are two fold. First, the term “casual” is used differently in practice (see Campbell and Burgess, 2001). By confining the sample to a single organization it was expected that the findings may not be influenced by the specific context in which the organization conducted its business and by the particular manufacturing sector environment in which it operates. Second, given the shortage of empirical research on permanent workers and casual workers (with long-term employment holding core jobs along with permanent workers side-by-side in the same work setting), we decided that the ideas presented in this article cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional survey. Therefore, we considered it is necessary to confine the research to a single industry and an organization within that industry in order to facilitate a manageable study, where both permanent and casual workers expose to the same work-based systems. We, therefore, considered focusing on a single organization is one of the strengths of the study to have a picture of workers’ job environment and their reactions to jobs, and in consequence, will be useful for deriving hypotheses about how permanent and casual workers holding core jobs side-by-side in organizations react to their jobs in future research studies.

The selected organisation, which is a part of a reputable group of companies in the business operations for more than a century in Sri Lanka, is one of the leading synthetic fibre brush and broom manufacturers and exporters in the country. The organisation manufactures its own synthetic fibres, and brush blocks and handles as production materials and those were used by the organisation in the manufacture of synthetic fibre brushes and brooms. The products manufactured by the organisation are mainly exported to the USA and Europe. By the end of December 2009, the organisation had 246 employees in total. Specifically, there were

12 managerial level employees, 32 administrative staff, and 202 operator level workers. All these employees were in the full-time employment. All the managerial and administrative level employees are in the permanent employment and they were not considered for this study. Of the 202 operator level workers, 92 were identified by the employer as permanent while 110 were identified as casuals. All permanent and casual workers belong to the categories of skilled and semi-skilled, and casual workers perform core job tasks along with permanent workers side-by-side in the manufacturing floor. However, casual workers are seen as lacking any entitlement to employment benefits tied to continuous service, such as annual salary increases, medical benefits, sick leave, payment for public holidays or other periods of non-work time, and they have limited protection against unfair dismissal. Wages of the casual workers are calculated on a daily basis and paid on a weekly basis.

Employees belong to any of the categories (such as management, administration, and operator level workers) of this organisation are not unionised although previous studies in the West identify trade unions as a form of voice that plays a major role in the system of regulation. The preliminary investigations made by us revealed that the non-existence of trade unions in the private sector in Sri Lanka is a common occurrence since the introduction of open economic policies in 1977 although employees' right to form and join trade unions is accepted by both the Sri Lankan government and employers (BOI, 2004).

The study population consisted of 202 operator level employees (92 permanent workers and 110 casual workers). This research was conducted as an independent study of the authors for academic purposes. An identical questionnaire was used to poll perceptions of permanent and casual workers. Participants were briefed the aims of the study prior to questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. Forty valid voluntarily completed questionnaires were received from each group of permanent and casual workers resulting in 43 and 36 percent response rate, respectively.

Table I shows demographic profiles of permanent and casual workers. With regard to demographics of the permanent workers, as can be seen in Table I, 83 per cent were male and 17 per cent were female. Of these, 27 per cent were single and 73 per cent were married. 10

per cent of the respondents had less than 10 years of schooling, 83 per cent had 10 years of schooling, and seven per cent had 12 years of schooling as the highest level of education. The mean age was 34 years (SD = 10). The average number of years of service in the present firm was nine years (SD = 7); the average number of years of service in the industry was 12 years (SD = 8). With regard to demographics of the casual workers, as can be seen in Table I, 68 per cent were male and 32 per cent were female. Of these, 50 per cent were single and 50 per cent were married. 32 per cent of the respondents had less than 10 years of schooling, 63 per cent had 10 years of schooling, and five per cent had 12 years of schooling as the highest level of education. The mean age was 31 years (SD = 11). The average number of years of service in the present firm was four years (SD = 2); the average number of years of service in the industry was seven years (SD = 5). Overall, the sample characteristics do not show considerable deviation from the population characteristics for both permanent and casual workers observed from organisational records.

TABLE I

Measures

All the measures were on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. For all measurement scales, Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria considered to be acceptable are eigenvalues not less than 1.0; the loadings 0.50 or greater; standardised Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure of 0.7 (see Hair et al., 2006). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for each construct (refer to Table II).

Job satisfaction. Job satisfaction was measured by the two items from Thatcher et al. (2002). The two items are "Generally speaking, I am very satisfied with this job" and "I am generally

satisfied with the kind of work I do". Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised alpha=.71; Eigenvalue=1.49; Explained variation=74%.

Organisational justice. The current study distinguishes between distributive justice and procedural justice. Distributive justice refers to the perceived fairness of various job outcomes workers receive such as job assignments (Roch and Shanock, 2006). Distributive justice was measured by the five items from Paré and Tremblay (2007). Example items are "I estimate my salary as being fair internally" and "My salary is fair in comparison with what is offered for a similar job elsewhere". Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised alpha=.81; Eigenvalue=2.80; Explained variation=61%.

Procedural justice referred to the perceived fairness of the means, rules and/or procedures used to determine those outcomes, for example to assign jobs (Ang and Slaughter, 2001; Roch and Shanock, 2006). Procedural justice was measured by the six items from Paré and Tremblay (2007). Example items are "The criteria used to grant promotions are clearly defined" and "In my work unit, the criteria used to grant pay raises are clearly defined". Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised alpha=.86; Eigenvalue=1.76; Explained variation=88%.

Work performance. Work performance implicitly means doing better or worse than comparable other (Price, 1997). Generally, self-report measures of individual performance were considered more appropriate because the individual is uniquely aware of the elements of high performance when the focus is on the perspective of the individual worker (refer to Rodwell et al., 1998). Work performance was measured by the five-item self-rating scale developed by Rodwell et al. (1998). Example items are "I am currently working at my best performance level" and "I am proud of my work performance". Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised alpha=.72; Eigenvalue=1.72; Explained variation=60%.

Methods of data collection and analysis

A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. The questionnaire was originally developed in English language. Since target respondents may not have a good command of English, self-administered survey questionnaire was translated into the native language, *Sinhala*. Then it was translated back from *Sinhala* to English. In translating from English to *Sinhala*, we assured the equivalence of the meaning of the measures that is used in native language as we adhered to the guidelines stipulated in the literature (see Andrews et al, 1994; Lynn, 2003). The translated questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of permanent and casual workers that fitted with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution. Participants of the survey were briefed on the aims of the study prior to data collection, and their responses were anonymous. The survey took approximately 15 minutes to complete.

The study relied on self-reported data. In this regard, Guest (2001, p. 1100) identifies three central problems in relation to self-reported measures, namely, positive response bias, the use of single-item measures, and the level of information possessed by the respondent. To overcome the first problem, factor analysis was used following the recommended guidelines by Hair et al. (2006). In the current study, to measure a particular variable, multiple item measures, which have demonstrated good reliability and validity in previous studies (e.g. two-item scale for job satisfaction from Thatcher et al. 2002) were used and attempted to overcome the second problem. Further, the standardised Cronbach's alpha values presented above also revealed that all measures were unidimensional. To overcome the third problem, as suggested by Guest (2001) more than one respondent was used. Further, we allowed respondents to respond to the questionnaire anonymously thus curtailing the motivation for self-presentation.

With regard to the methods of data analysis, in addition to descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test, and logistic regression were used to investigate differences in the work outcomes of permanent and casual workers. For the logistic regression, casual worker is coded as "0" and permanent worker is coded as "1".

Results

Table II shows differences in work outcomes by employment status. There are significant differences between permanent and casual workers in their perceptions of job satisfaction ($p < .01$), procedural justice ($p < .01$) and work performance ($p < .001$), where permanent workers reported more positive perceptions than casuals.

TABLE II

Table III shows means, standard deviations, and zero-order correlations between all the variables. As can be seen in Table III, job satisfaction ($p < .05$), procedural justice ($p < .05$), and work performance ($p < .01$) are positively related to employment status. However, distributive justice is not significantly correlated with employment status.

TABLE III

Logistic regression was used to investigate differences in perceptions between permanent and casual workers. Logistic regression obtained Nagelkerke R^2 value of 0.66, which suggested that 66 per cent of the variance is explained by the covariates. P value of 0.55 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test also suggested a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 73 (72.5%).

The results of the logistic regression are shown in Table IV. It is evident from Table IV that job satisfaction, procedural justice and work performance are important work outcomes that discriminate between permanent and casual workers. For the study, casual worker is coded as "0" and permanent worker is coded as "1". Therefore, the odds of permanent workers to perceive a higher level of job satisfaction (as opposed to casual workers) are two times (2.44) as high. This supports H1. Further, the odds of permanent workers to perceive a higher

level of procedural justice (as opposed to casual workers) are almost two times (1.98) as high. This supports H3. Similarly, the odds of permanent workers to perceive a higher level of work performance (as opposed to casual workers) are 18 times (18.43) as high. This supports H4. However, distributive justice was not identified as an important work outcome that discriminates between permanent and casual workers. Hence, H2 is partially supported.

TABLE IV

Conclusions and implications

It was found that the perceptions of permanent and casual workers pertaining to the work-related outcomes are different, where casual workers are likely to exhibit significantly poorer work outcomes compared to permanent workers for job satisfaction, procedural justice, and work performance.

Although we are aware of the fact that this is a broad and complex field, confining the study to a single organisation facilitated a manageable study with the homogeneity of the sample, where both permanent and casual workers subject to the same work-based systems. The organisation studied has been substantially using casual workers along with permanent workers in the manufacturing floor. The employment data of the organization reveal two important aspects. First, the number of casual workers employed is far beyond the number employed as permanent workers. The number of casual workers employed in the organisation is 110 and the number employed as permanent workers is 92. Forrier and Sels (2003) suggest that an indicator reflecting the level of contractual flexibility is the number of employees with the casual employment arrangement as a percentage of the total number of workers (202). This percentage for the organization studied is 54 per cent ($110/202 \times 100$).

Second, casual workers' average tenure in the present workplace is beyond three years. This implies long-term and regular work but deprived of standard employment benefits. Hence, it could be argued that there is a group of "long-term casuals", whose participation in

casual employment is characterised by lengthy tenure and substantial regularity in daily and weekly hours of employment. As pointed out by Watson (2005), this situation suggests not only the increased numbers of casuals at work, but also the process of casualization, the conversion of existing non-casual jobs into casual jobs, especially in industrial sectors not traditionally associated with casual work, such as export manufacturing. This trend reinforces concerns with the implications of inferior conditions of employment. An issue, however, that this research has not attempted to address is the driving forces behind the development of a secondary workforce in the organization. The possible reasons might be that the organization has identified the advantages of such an adaptation as a means of coping with workforce non-unionization, cost cutting initiatives, and the need to cover temporary labour shortages. All the employees in this organization are not unionized. The literature points out possibilities of the existence of a symbiotic relationship in which the weakness of trade unions and the increase in flexible working have reinforced each other (see Croucher and Brewster, 1998). However, the increased usage of casual workforce points to the organization being no more than “opportunists” in the sense of its strategic employment requirements, i.e., responding as best as they could to events as they unfurl. Although the utilization of casual workers provides extensive labour flexibility with reduced obligation on their behalf, gaining immediate benefits to the bottom line, the organization may find their competitive advantage disappears in the long term. However, the implication of such developments for casual workers is negative in terms of aggregate skill acquisition, employment security and the sustainability of employment conditions. Dessler (1999) also points out that although no organization can guarantee job security, incurring costs associated with training employees without giving them some prospects of promotion or job security may indeed be self-defeating.

Results suggest significant differences between permanent and casual workers in terms of their job satisfaction, procedural justice and work performance, where casual workers reported significantly low levels of job satisfaction, procedural justice and work performance compared to permanent workers. However, there were no significant differences between the permanent and casual workers with respect to distributive justice. The findings of the current

study that there are significant differences between job satisfaction of permanent and casual workers supports the findings of previous research (such as Paramio and Zofío, 2008), which provided evidence that workers on nonstandard employment may exhibit less job satisfaction than permanent workers. The study investigated both distributive justice and procedural justice to investigate organisational justice perceptions. We found significant differences between procedural justice of permanent and casual workers although we did not find any differences between distributive justice of permanent and casual workers. As suggested by Paré and Tremblay (2007) (although not in a similar context) a potential explanation for this finding may be that the perceptions of unfair treatment with regard to procedures and rules may be perceived as much less important by permanent and casual workers since they had experiences of changing the work environment time to time by switching employers without much difficulty in the past. The data provided in Table I also support this contention.

However, it should be noted that we have not come across previous empirical studies that has a resemblance to the current study in the context of developed market economies. Further, we have not come across any literature on the use of labour flexibility strategies from less developed economies. Therefore, the current study was conducted as a pilot study that confined to a single organisation to establish baseline data and to be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research. In this context, the findings of this study make a contribution to the literature by studying perceptions of workers in permanent and non-standard employment, casual in particular, who perform the same job tasks side-by-side in the same work setting. However, more empirical work is needed to test our propositions and to replicate, extend, or disconfirm the results presented in this article.

All the casuals employed in the organization are employer-defined casuals who had been in the same job for several years. Hence, it could be argued that these casuals are not “genuine” casuals who are engaged irregularly and for intermittent, short periods. Rather, they are provided with regular work but insecurity of tenure, without redundancy pay and without rights to annual or sick leave. In the Sri Lankan context, employers have a greater degree of autonomy in developing people management strategies which contribute to numerical labour

flexibility independently of environmental factors. This is mainly due to sizeable gaps in the regulatory system in Sri Lanka. Ambiguity, confusion and the absence of regulations surrounds the non-standard employment arrangement in Sri Lanka has created an environment within which casual employment, as unprotected employment with markedly inferior rights and benefits, survives and even flourishes. However, people management strategies should be a result of developments in the institutional environment rather than firm-level rational decision making. Consequently the organization's people management strategies should be a product of evolving conceptions of the individual, and of individual rights, that become institutionalized in labour legislation.

Overall, for most of the last century, the employment relationship was based on permanent employment as the primary work arrangement. However, in recent years, there has been a move towards a variety of non-standard employment arrangements such as casual (Burgess et al., 2008; Standing, 2008). Therefore, it could be expected that the use of casual workers along with permanent workers, especially performing the same job duties, should obviously be a concern for many organisations worldwide. However, the understanding of the impact of employment status on work outcomes is extremely limited (see Chattopadhyay and George, 2001; Davis-Blake et al., 2003). Therefore, the findings presented in this article and conclusions and implications drawn could provide useful information to derive hypotheses about how permanent and causal workers working side-by-side in organizations react to their jobs.

Limitations and future research

The small scale of this study tends to limit the potential for generalisation. However, as detailed in the section on *sample*, concentrating on a single firm as advantages. Given the shortage of empirical research on this topic, alongside the growing use of nonstandard employment arrangements, clearly there is a need for further research in this area. The ideas presented in this article cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional pilot study and those need to be tested over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts that

compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. Such studies will be able to obtain a deeper and richer understanding of their jobs, roles, and tasks and how differences in the work environment may contribute to differences in their work attitudes, behaviours, and performance. However, it should be noted that there are difficulties in comparing across countries as the different meanings that the associated term (i.e., casual) have in the different parts of the world (such as Europe and Australia) (see Campbell and Burgess, 2001). Last but not least, as detailed in the section on *theoretical background*, interrelationships between work outcomes are beyond the focus of this study and have not been investigated as a result. Future studies with larger samples can investigate such relationships.

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Tables

Table I. Sample characteristics

	Permanent (N=40)	Casual (N=40)
Gender:		
Male	83%	68%
Female	17%	32%
Marital status:		
Married	73%	50%
Single	27%	50%
Education:		
Less than 10 years	10%	32%
Ten years	83%	63%
12 years	7%	5%
Age:		
Mean	34.75	30.89
Median	35.50	26.00
Mode	38.00	21.00
SD	9.51	10.81
Years of work experience with the present employer:		
Mean	8.79	3.54
Median	6.00	3.00
Mode	6.00	6.00
SD	6.78	2.43
Total years of work experience:		
Mean	12.22	7.07
Median	10.00	5.50
Mode	6.00	3.00
SD	7.60	5.43

Table II. Differences in work outcomes by employment status

	Permanent		Casual		t	Sig.
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Job satisfaction	4.23	.68	3.81	.79	2.56	.006**
Procedural justice	3.26	.81	2.76	.85	2.71	.004**
Distributive justice	2.51	.96	2.35	.86	.927	.185
Work performance	4.67	.33	4.35	.42	3.75	.000***

Note: **p<.01; ***p<.001.

Table III. Correlations

	1	2	3	4
1. Employment status	1			
2. Job satisfaction	.279*	1		
3. Procedural justice	.270*	.064	1	
4. Distributive justice	.104	.382**	.308**	1
5. Work performance	.391**	.201	.193	.121

Note: * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table IV. Summarised results of logistic regression

	B	S.E.	Wald	Exp(B)
Job satisfaction	.893	.418	4.560	2.442*
Procedural justice	.682	.268	6.458	1.978*
Distributive justice	.475	.350	1.844	.622
Work performance	2.914	.835	12.178	18.432***
Constant	17.891	4.523	15.648	2.234***

Note: * p<.05; ***p<0.001.